

Bandpass Filter Based on 3-D-Printed Ceramic Resonators

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Abstract—A dielectric-loaded cavity filter working in the Ku-band with wide bandwidth and high selectivity is presented. The structure is composed of rectangular waveguide cavities loaded with 3-D-printed dielectric resonators. An example of a 4-pole filter is shown in this paper. The filter has three rectangular cavities loaded with three dielectric resonators made of alumina. The dielectrics have a hexagonal shape and have been designed as a single piece. They operate with the dielectric mode $TE_{01\delta}$ and the cavity mode TE_{101} . More specifically, the mode $TE_{01\delta}$ was exploited for cavities 1 and 3, whereas modes $TE_{01\delta}$ and TE_{101} were exploited for the middle cavity. These combinations of modes were used in order to obtain transmission zeros (TZs) in the upper and lower stopband of the filter, and obtain as a result, a high-selective filtering response. For validation purposes, a 4-pole filter working in the Ku-band at 14.125 GHz, with 5.3% fractional bandwidth was fabricated and measured.

Index Terms—3-D printing, additive manufacturing (AM), bandpass filter, ceramic, dielectric resonator, rectangular waveguide, transmission zero (TZ).

I. INTRODUCTION

Generally speaking, different microwave filters based on different technologies can be employed depending on the application they are intended to be used. When it comes to space communications, at the early stages of the communication system, waveguide and dielectric loaded-cavities filters are usually the most common options. This is due to their high Q -factor and high-power handling capabilities. The downside of waveguide filters comes down to its size, whereas the use of dielectric materials can help to reduce their size thanks to the dielectric permittivity of the resonators. In addition to this, they can also provide good thermal stability. Nevertheless, nowadays the demands for new communications with more stringent requirements is pushing towards the development of new filters with more characteristics. Some of the challenges involved in the design of dielectric-loaded filters consist of achieving high bandwidths (BWs) since the fields are concentrated in the dielectric puck, making it hard to couple to the other loaded-cavities. It is also challenging to obtain transmission zeros (TZs) in an inline structure, something that is important for obtaining pseudo-elliptic filters.

Fig. 1. Proposed 4-pole filter.

Fig. 2. Electric field of: (a) dielectric mode $TE_{01\delta}$ and (b) cavity mode TE_{101} .

Several filter configurations have been reported in the past. Most of them working with coaxial feeding probes for input and output, as in [1], where dielectric pucks have been used to load TM cavities in an inline structure, with TZs that were obtained by exploiting nonresonating modes. Nonresonating modes for obtaining TZs in an inline filter have also been exploited in [2], but in that case, the resonant mode was the $TE_{01\delta}$. Solutions involving waveguides for input and output can be seen in [3] or [4]. The latter using 3-D printing techniques for the dielectric resonators. In [5] instead, a mix of two dielectric modes, the $TE_{01\delta}$ mode and the cavity mode TE_{101} were employed in order to obtain TZs in an inline structure. Similar to [5], in this paper, we propose a new dielectric-loaded filter configuration (see Fig. 1) with high BW and capable of generating TZs in an inline structure. The

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. Dielectric-loaded resonator. (a) Changing the height. (b) Changing the length.

dielectrics were designed to be manufactured by means of a 3-D printer as a single piece without the need of additional low-permittivity dielectric elements, which are normally used for holding the high-permittivity dielectric resonators as to maintain them detached from the cavity walls.

II. DIELECTRIC PUCK

An example of a dielectric-loaded cavity fed by means of input-output waveguides sections is shown in Fig. 2. This configuration consists of a cylindrical puck enclosed within a rectangular waveguide cavity. The dielectric material is alumina with a permittivity of 9.5. The excited modes are: the dielectric mode $TE_{01\delta}$ [Fig. 2(a)] and the cavity mode TE_{101} [Fig. 2(b)]. Some clarifications are necessary regarding the name of the modes. The exploited resonators consist of a cavity loaded with a dielectric puck. In this complex structure, modes cannot be simply divided into TE and TM. The mode we called TE_{101} is actually similar to the cavity mode TE_{101} , but the presence of the puck slightly perturbs the field distribution so that it is no longer a TE mode, however, here the name TE_{101} mode is maintained for the sake of simplicity.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Dual-mode resonator. Case (a) $f_2 > f_1$ and case (b) $f_1 > f_2$.

Something similar happens to the $TE_{01\delta}$ mode. In that case, the mode is very similar to the dielectric mode $TE_{01\delta}$, but it is slightly perturbed by the presence of the cavity. Again, the name has been maintained for ease of reference. As can be seen from Fig. 2, the electric field of the mode $TE_{01\delta}$ forms a circular pattern around the dielectric puck. The resonance frequency can be controlled mainly by the dimensions of the puck (radius and thickness). On the other hand, the mode TE_{101} is a loaded-cavity mode and the dimensions of the cavity can control its resonant frequency, besides the physical parameters of the puck. Fig. 3 shows the scattering parameters of a dielectric-loaded cavity connected by means of input-output waveguides sections, and as can be seen, two modes are excited, the lower resonant frequency, which represents the mode TE_{101} (f_1), and the higher resonant frequency that represents the mode $TE_{01\delta}$ (f_2). Two geometrical parameters of the rectangular cavity (see inset of Fig. 3) can be used to understand the changes produced in these modes. In particular, Fig. 3(a) shows the variation of the cavity height, and Fig. 3(b) the variation of the cavity length. When changing the height of the cavity towards higher values, the TZ moves

Fig. 5. Routine scheme (a) and simulated results (b) of a 3-pole filter.

closer to the $TE_{01\delta}$. The TZ is generated as a consequence of the mode TE_{101} . When increasing the height, the coupling of the mode TE_{101} increases more than that of the mode $TE_{01\delta}$. The reduction of this coupling can be compensated by changing the apertures. In addition to this, the radius of the dielectric can also be slightly modified in order to obtain the same resonant frequency of the mode $TE_{01\delta}$ before the modifications. Moreover, it can also be shown how the resonant frequency of the mode TE_{101} increases. Alternatively, Fig. 3(b) shows how lowering the length of the cavity moves the resonance frequency of the mode TE_{101} closer to that of the mode $TE_{01\delta}$. Must be taking into account that the length of the resonator changes the coupling of both modes, when reducing the length, the coupling increases, so the apertures in this case were reduced in order to obtain the same initial coupling values. As a result, a dual-mode resonator based on a mix of TE_{101} and $TE_{01\delta}$ modes can be obtained when considering the height and length of the cavity. Fig. 4 shows a dual-mode resonator with different positions of the TZ. This can be achieved by lowering the length of the cavity and increasing its height. At a certain point, the frequency of the mode TE_{101} (f_1) becomes higher than the frequency of the mode $TE_{01\delta}$ (f_2), moving the TZ from higher to lower frequencies, as can be seen in Fig. 4(b).

III. FILTER DESIGN

Different filter configurations could be obtained as a result of changing the dimensions of the rectangular waveguide cavities. An example of a common filter configuration consists

Fig. 6. Routine scheme (a) and simulated results (b) of the proposed 4-pole filter.

Fig. 7. Simulated results of a 4-pole filter for different BWs.

of a classical inductive waveguide filter loaded with dielectrics operating with the mode $TE_{01\delta}$. This can be observed in Fig. 5, where a 3-pole is shown along with its routing scheme. This filter was designed in order to operate only with the dielectric mode $TE_{01\delta}$. Additionally, Fig. 5 shows the mode TE_{101} in the lower stopband. In this case, the BW of the filter was exploited as to obtain its maximum value. In fact, it can be observed from the inset of Fig. 5(b), that input-output apertures are completely opened.

On the other hand, Fig. 6 shows the routing scheme and the simulation of a 4-pole filter. The inset of Fig. 6(b) shows

Fig. 8. (a) Classical cylindrical puck. (b) Hexagonal puck.

Fig. 9. Cad view of the mechanical design.

the geometry of the structure, which consists of three cavities: input-output cavities have been designed in order to excite only the mode $TE_{01\delta}$, while the middle cavity has been designed in order to work as a dual-mode resonator, similar to Fig. 4(b), with a TZ in the lower stopband. Since input-output cavities have the resonant frequency of the mode $TE_{01\delta}$ higher than that of the mode TE_{101} , another TZ in the upper stopband is present, similar to the response of Fig. 3. As shown in Fig. 6, the filter presents a BW of 750 MHz, and has a total of three TZs close to the passband. In addition, the lower stopband is free of spurious, whereas the upper stopband presents a spurious mode at $f_0 \cdot 1.27$. An advantage of such a structure is the reduction of the filters length. However, the Q -factor of the cavity operating with the mode TE_{101} will be smaller. The mode $TE_{01\delta}$ presents a high theoretical Q -factor, about 9000 at 14.9 GHz, whereas the theoretical Q -factor of the mode TE_{101} is 6500 at 12 GHz (considering an aluminum cavity with a height of 9.53 mm, a length of 12 mm and a $\tan \delta = 8 \cdot 10^{-5}$). Moreover, since narrowing the length of the cavity allows increasing the coupling without the need of

Fig. 10. Images: (a) fabricated dielectric puck. (b) Cad view of the dielectric puck with the silicone support. (c) Dielectric tuning element. (d) Dielectric glued to the screw.

changing the apertures of the cavity, filters with higher BWs can also be designed while saving space in an inline structure, and for a relatively small dielectric permittivity. Additionally, the use of dielectrics to connect all the resonators adds an additional degree of freedom that can be used to increase the coupling between resonators. Fig. 7 shows an example of two different BWs (0.75 GHz and 1.26 GHz) based on the same filter configuration.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

For validation purposes, a 4-pole filter like the one in the inset of Fig. 6(b) was fabricated. The filter uses WR75 input-output waveguides sections and it is centered at 14.125 GHz with a fractional bandwidth (FBW) of 5.3%. Alumina was used as a dielectric and was provided by the company Lithoz. The alumina had a specified value of the dielectric permittivity of 9.5 and $\tan \delta = 0.00008 (8 \cdot 10^{-5})$. Must be noticed that in the inset of Fig. 6(b), the dielectric resonators have a different shape and they are united as a single piece. The dielectric has a hexagonal shape as shown in Fig. 8. This was done in order to reduce the manufacturing tolerances of the dielectric, and have just a single piece that avoids the use of external dielectric elements, which would help to suspend the dielectric resonators. Instead, two supports were added to the dielectric puck in order to be connected to the lateral walls of the cavity. This can be seen in Fig. 9. Furthermore, Fig. 10(a) shows the manufactured puck along with the cad view (Fig. 10(b)). External elements for adjusting the frequency were also used [see inset of Fig. 6(b)]. Metallic screws were incorporated horizontally similar to [5] in order to adjust the frequency of the dielectric mode $TE_{01\delta}$, instead, for the mode TE_{101} , a small

Fig. 11. Comparison between measured and simulated results of the fabricated 4-pole filter.

cylindrical dielectric of alumina with the same permittivity as the dielectric resonators was used, and inserted vertically. The puck was also fabricated by Lithoz and glued on top of a metallic screw [see Fig. 10(c) and (b)].

Results are shown in Fig. 11, which were obtained using the commercial software ANSYS High-Frequency Structure Simulator (HFSS). It can be observed that there is a frequency shift of about 0.38 GHz, which could not be recovered with the external elements. This is due to the dielectric constant of the manufactured alumina that is sensibly different from the nominal value considered in the simulations. The minimum return loss is 9 dB throughout the frequency band. The average insertion loss is about 0.6 dB (calculated as an average value), which accounts for the losses of the dielectric resonators and cavity, but also for the reflection losses. The measured unloaded Q -factor is 4000, as opposed to the simulated one with a value of 5600 (considering aluminum for the cavity). It was observed that a permittivity of 10.05 seemed to match well with the measured results, this is shown in Fig. 12, where no other elements but the dielectric permittivity were changed. The work is still in progress and, in the future, other prototypes with a more accurate estimation of the dielectric constant will be manufactured.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A loaded-cavity filter that uses 3-D-printed ceramics resonators has been presented in the paper. The filter uses a combination of the modes $TE_{01\delta}$ and TE_{101} in order to achieve selective responses in an inline structure. A 4-pole filter formed by three dielectric-loaded cavities: two operating with the dielectric mode $TE_{01\delta}$ and one dielectric-loaded cavity operating with the modes TE_{101} and $TE_{01\delta}$. A 4-pole filter was designed and fabricated. Results exhibit a good measured Q -factor, but show a frequency shift of the response due to a variation of the permittivity.

Fig. 12. Comparison between measured and simulated results using a different permittivity.

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